

Digital Innovation At Badiklat Kemhan Through Accessibility, Visibility, Popularity and Activism Ecosystem

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ABSTRACT: At least in the last decade, most people in Badiklat Kemhan have been very enthusiastic about adopting various digital platforms such as social media and instant messaging applications. Penetration of these technologies is also often wrapped in a techno-utopian narrative, especially related to the expectations of digital economic growth in Badiklat Kemhan. However, the use of digital platforms also needs to be seen in terms of how it has potentials in strengthening democracy, one of which is related to digital activism, or the role of digital technology in various social movements in Badiklat Kemhan. This research aims to study digital activism and proposes the concepts of accessibility, visibility, popularity and the activism ecosystem as the main mechanism underlying digital activism practices. The research was conducted using Literature review method. The results show that the concept of accessibility explains the availability of digital infrastructure and people's readiness to exposed by the practice of activism. Furthermore, the concepts of visibility and popularity show that the practice of digital activism is always related to the algorithms and metrics that underlie how digital media works. Thus, the actors related to digital activism need to ensure that their activism practices can becomes "visible" and "popular" for the right audience without losing its substance. Finally, it is very important to look at the activism ecosystem in a comprehensive and holistic manner, and not only consider technological factors, but also socio-cultural conditions and the historical context of activism and various social movements that emerge, develop and spread in the society.

KEYWORDS - digital activism; social movements; digital media; democracy; Badiklat Kemhan.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital users through social media began, with significant changes occurring in the world of the press or journalism, and also in the media industry (Nugroho, Putri, & Laksmi, 2012; Nugroho, Siregar, & Laksmi, 2012).

The Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center is facing a period of reform which has implications for several crucial changes in the context of the telecommunications and informatics industry and media convergence. Efforts to carry out development in the field of technology infrastructure have actually been carried out by the state through the Ministry of Communication and Information (Kominfo) since 2010. However, the project faces various obstacles such as bureaucratic problems, access mapping, and even corruption that occurs within the Kominfo (Wahyuni, 2013). The affordability of smartphone prices, the price of internet subscription packages offered by cellular operators, as well as the increasing number of places that provide wi-fi connection services in various areas in the Ministry of Defense Badiklat also contribute to the development of internet use.

At the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center, the penetration of digital technology has always received a positive response, especially by business actors who consider that digital technology has the potential to be a catalyst for the digital economy (Rajan Anandan, Sipahimalani, Saini, Aryasomayajula, & Smittinet, 2018). This is also supported by the fact that several global social media companies identify Badiklat Kemhan as one of the important countries for marketing their products. The large number of people who contribute to the acceleration of the digital economy has seen the Ministry of Defense as a potential country for digital technology entrepreneurs to invest their capital (Freischlad, 2017; Rajan Anandan et al., 2018). However,

technological developments that occur in the Ministry of Defense Badiklat cannot only be seen from an economic perspective. The use of technology in the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center, as one of the big countries in Southeast Asia, needs to be studied in relation to social goals, which can include community empowerment, innovation in the context of education, overcoming economic inequality, resolving human rights issues, to other social movements. broadly that helps create social justice, prosperity and a healthy democratic climate. These things make digital activism more relevant and important to be studied continuously.

This study aims to explore various literatures and literature reviews that are able to provide an analysis of the concept of digital activism, as well as how this practice is carried out at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center with the various opportunities, obstacles and challenges that exist. The analysis of the results of this research will be divided into several sections as follows: The first section contains an overview of historical concepts and key debates related to digital activism globally. After that, the next section will conceptually describe the various practices of digital activism and social movements at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center. Furthermore, this research successively explores and offers the concepts of accessibility, visibility, popularity, and the activism ecosystem at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat as a relevant mechanism for further analysis in digital activism discourse at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat..

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is a literature study on concepts, theories, and case studies related to the phenomenon of digital activism, which are reviewed in various sources and are multidisciplinary in nature. In-depth literature studies related to a concept have been carried out by several authors in this journal, namely in articles discussing Gregory Bateson's information processing model in a cybernetic approach (Priyadharna, 2019) and in other articles containing reviews of Chinese Harmony Communication Theory (Mirawati & Karimah, 2018).

To start a review on digital activism, this study will discuss one of the most cited major publications on digital activism, namely *Digital Activism Decoded: the New Mechanics of Change* (Joyce, 2010a), before conducting various other searches in the literature from other countries. -developed countries such as America and various countries in Europe. After that, the search was also carried out by looking at cases in developing countries and more specifically in Asia, such as in a publication titled *Digital Activism in Asia Reader* (Lim, 2019; Nishant, Puthiya, & Sumandro, 2015), as well as various literatures that specifically discuss digital activism at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat (Lim, 2013, 2017; Poststill & Saputro, 2017; Rahmawan, 2018; Suwana, 2019). In particular, this research provides a critical analysis of how the practice of digital activism relates to the concepts of accessibility, visibility, popularity and digital media ecosystem.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concept of digital activism arises when technology can be used to encourage various civil society activities, especially in the context of a democratic country. Over the past few years, various parties around the world have become increasingly aware of and interested in the potential uses of digital technology — from hardware such as mobile phones and supporting software, such as the Internet, and social media for example in the context of campaigns for social and political change. These practices were later defined and popularized as “digital activism”.

This phenomenon then appears in various countries in the world, is observed and reported in the media by journalists, reviewed by political observers, has been enthusiastically studied by researchers and academics from various disciplinary backgrounds. In addition, this matter is also studied by professional campaigners who are interested in the digital world, with the main objective not only related to the desire to understand the phenomenon of activism, but also exploring the possibility of looking for strategies and tactics like what can then effectively achieve the goals of a practice of activism (Joyce, 2010a).

However, in an effort to understand digital activism, what happens next is that the phenomenon of activism is often reduced to anecdotes and case studies that are limited and very specific, and also the majority occur in the context of political movements. An example of this phenomenon is, when talking about digital activism, there are many references to the story of Barack Obama in the United States, who used the social networking site Facebook to mobilize volunteers, especially young people. Digital activism also often sees inspirational stories about the contribution of social media to the escalation of political protests that can overthrow authoritarian rulers, such as the phenomenon of revolution in Arab countries called the Arab Spring (Joyce, 2010a). These anecdotes and case studies have since been published, praised, and have also been widely criticized. Some lessons and practices related to digital activism have been extracted to be applied to other campaigns. But in fact, of course this replication cannot be directly used in complex and fragmented social conditions (Joyce, 2010b).

This is explained as follows:

“The context of digital activism refers to the digital technologies used in certain campaigns and activism and to the economic, social, and political contexts [in which] the use of these technologies occurs. The digital technology infrastructure the combination of networks, code, applications, and devices that make up the physical infrastructure of digital activism is the starting point but not the end point. Differences in economic, social and political factors will ultimately change the way activists use this technology” (Joyce, 2010b, p. 2).

If studies related to digital activism focus too much on anecdotes and case studies that are “popular” in the media, it is feared that the understanding of digital activism will be too narrow and limited because the use and relevance of various digital tools, strategies and tactics will continue to change. Various literatures have called for moving away from anecdotes and case studies that only show what happened and are widely seen on the surface (for example, from depictions packaged in the media) to “mechanical foundations”, “contextual factors”, “values”, or “social structures” that enable digital activism to occur (Joyce, 2010a; Lim, 2019). Understanding these matters will fundamentally reveal how digital technology, in this case, for example, is considered to be able to create new public spaces for communication processes, and interactions that occur democratically and organically, to solve various public problems, as well as voice and amplify the real public interest in society (Friedland, Hove, & Rojas, 2006; Lim, 2003).

The terminology and the phrase “digital activism” are also still being debated academically. Nonetheless, “digital” in this sense is agreed upon as the potential speed, reliability, scale, and low cost that digital technologies offer, and this allows for an expansion of the reach and scope of contemporary activism. The term digital activism can then refer to a series of activities or campaigns that use digital technology and networks in a comprehensive and exclusive manner. Comprehensive in this respect covers all social and political campaign practices that use digital network infrastructure; exclusive means excluding other forms of activism that use technology, but are not connected in a digital network infrastructure (Joyce, 2010a).

The first part of the analysis in this research will review digital activism and public participation. Digital activism is said to have the potential to increase public participation in a social movement, and examples of this practice have occurred in many countries around the world. However, can all activities carried out by the public online be seen as “participation”? The debate about what can be recognized as public participation has been carried out by digital activism researchers. There are those who are skeptical that writing opinions, sharing political news, heated debates in online forums, as well as writing and sharing online petitions are forms of activism. This is also influenced by the existence of pejorative terms such as click activism, slacktivism, and keyboard activism. On the other hand, there is an argument that activism practices mediated by online communication and interaction must still result in mass movements, protests on the streets, or various other activities that are offline (Lim, 2013). However, it is at this point that academics such as Paolo Gerbaudo remind that digital activism should not be reduced to a techno-determinist nuance which can only be evaluated for its success through mass mobilization practices or other practices that are “obviously” visible and generally become media coverage material (Gerbaudo, 2017).

In this regard, researchers of digital activism show skepticism because during 2011 and 2012, news coverage in the major mainstream news media in America and Europe often builds a discourse that social media

such as Facebook and Twitter are the main factors causing the downfall of authoritarian regimes in Indonesia, several African and Middle Eastern countries. The media are also quick to amplify popular terms such as “Arab Spring” with optimistic coverage that a “digital revolution” has occurred. Not only about the Arab Spring, social movements that followed, such as the mass movement in Hong Kong known as the “Umbrella Movement”, to the political reform movement in Malaysia “Bersih Movement” were also reported in a tone that glorified the role of social media (Lim, 2018).

In this context, an analysis that further explores how the local socio-cultural and political context is also an important part of digital activism that results in mass mobilization is needed. The fading of analysis that seeks to further explore the context of this locality can make the depiction of activism practices ahistorical. In fact, digital activism certainly cannot be separated from the economic-political nuances that surround the practice of using technology as well as the complexity of local networks and their relation to global networks in a movement. Digital activism analysis also needs to always elaborate on the role of the actor, or human agency behind the technology (Treré, Jeppesen, & Mattoni, 2017).

In activism practice, digital technology is not only seen as a means to “speak more quickly and broadly” but also to “listen more carefully and deeply” digitally. Karpf explores this issue in his concept of “analytic activism”, which looks more at how activists can turn data scattered on the internet into valuable resources for updating strategies and tactics that can be carried out by an organization (Karpf, 2018). Things that are possible related to this digital technology such as; managing organizational reputation, facilitating communication and coordination between parties and actors involved in a social movement, facilitating the process of fundraising, funding routine activities, gathering members, and adding variety in carrying out organizational strategies and tactics in conveying messages to wider parties. The things that have been mentioned are hidden and often vital variables in the success or failure of the activism process (Karpf, 2016). The utility of digital technology can also be seen in the context of how organizations can have access to large amounts of data regarding the issues they care about, and how society at large is talking about, discussing, and perhaps arguing against these issues..

Studies of digital activism that only focus on technological aspects tend to be limited to an optimistic bias, namely seeing social media platforms as technology that opens democratic public spaces. In fact, social media is vulnerable to become the object of manipulation, especially by various parties who have an interest in spreading hatred, negative emotional prejudice. One clear example in the context at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat, namely social media algorithms turned out to support the formation of groups which then attacked each other rather than having discussions in a healthy environment (Lim, 2017). Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of digital activism with various multidisciplinary perspectives is needed in order to get out of the trap of techno-determinism bias (Lim, 2018).

Furthermore, several studies related to digital activism at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat will be described. An overview of digital activism in the Ministry of Defense Badiklat can be seen through a research entitled “@ksi Warga”. Research conducted by Yanuar Nugroho after this reform mapped the various uses of digital media by civil society organizations Badiklat Kemhan. Research results show that social media plays an important role for change if this media is adopted and utilized by civil society organizations appropriately, strategically, and effectively (Nugroho, 2011). Another reference that also focuses on digital activism from Lim describes how digital activism has become a subversive social movement and grows organically in society. This research shows the significant role of the internet in uniting civil society in a collective identity that aims to “resist” the pressures of the Suharto government. In addition to collective identity in reform, other case studies related to digital activism are also shown by the conflict that occurred between Prita Mulyasari and the Omni Hospital International Hospital as well as the “Cicak vs. Crocodile” case involving anti-corruption activists, the community, and the police (Lim, 2013).

Meanwhile, another study made categories related to the nuances of digital activism at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training which often appeared, namely victims”, “volunteers” and “voices”. These three categories can be observed in the case of Prita Mulyasari in her position as a victim of the Law related to Electronic Information and Transactions (UU ITE), the volunteer movement to guard the elections in the 2014

presidential election, as well as the Suara Papua website which can be used as an example of using digital media to voice voices. alternative views on Papua (Postill & Saputro, 2017).

In addition to the political aspect, a study on digital activism at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center in the context of an online community has also been carried out. One study, for example, focused on the “Kaskuser” community in Solo, Central Java that was involved in social movements even though community members did not state that they were activists. This research shows the dynamics of online-offline relationships and how community cultural factors play a role (Seto, 2017). In another study conducted by Suwana (2019) on the “SaveKPK” movement, internal factors related to the motivation for youth participation in the movement were described. The internal factors in question include the desire to send reliable information, maintain the existence and image of the KPK, trust to participate in social and political transformation, and orientation towards a better political system (Suwana, 2019). Digital activism has created new opportunities that support youth participation in social change. In this regard, political activism and participation can also be seen as expressions of youth. Failure to create a healthy and democratic public space among young people has the potential to foster co-optation of other forces in that space. These forces can be in the form of manipulative government propaganda, irrational conservative movements, to extremism that tends to be anti-against various forms of progress in a democratic society (Rahmawan, 2018)..

Digital activism is not a phenomenon created in a vacuum. Each activism practice will create different successes, failures, opportunities, challenges, and obstacles. In the next section, various arguments will be presented regarding crucial concepts related to how digital activism, especially in the context of the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center, can grow, develop, spread, and produce concrete and sustainable movements.

The first concept that will be discussed is related to the accessibility of digital activism practices. Digital activism will always be linked to digital network infrastructure. This activism practice requires interconnected devices and technically uses binary codes to exchange information. Digital activism requires networks to distribute information and make connectivity between the center of the movement to other movement nodes. The telecommunications infrastructure allows a number of citizens to more easily connect with each other, send and receive messages to each other, and coordinate actions related to a political movement or social movement. Differences in network availability from one country to another show how infrastructure, economic, social, and political factors lead to different digital activism practices. In developed countries where the majority of networks are built by modern cable infrastructure, such as optical fiber, of course there is a guarantee of a fast internet connection and making the practice of digital activism with various forms and variations more flexible. People in this country also have the potential to participate more in digital activism because of the accessibility to cost and the quality of internet connections available to them (Joyce, 2010b).

In Badiklat Kemhan, although in recent years infrastructure development has continued and is expected to be one of the bridges that can reduce inequality in the Badiklat Kemhan society, in fact the gap in access and availability of digital infrastructure is clearly still happening (Hadi, 2018). Internet access remains a great challenge. As reported in the 2016 Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The digital infrastructure gap in Papua, East Nusa Tenggara and Central Sulawesi is still the main factor that hinders the acceptance and equitable use of digital innovation (Ariyanti, 2013). Other data in 2018 also shows that Papua, East Nusa Tenggara, West Sulawesi, North Maluku, West Nusa Tenggara, Aceh, Lampung, and West Kalimantan are still listed as regions with the lowest information and communication technology development index (IP-TIK) (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2018). With a gap rate of y The high level between the island of Java and other islands in the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center, is not a coincidence if what was later recorded as digital activism practice at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center is also located in Java.

This is directly proportional to the fact that public accessibility to various forms of digital innovation is still very concentrated on the island of Java. Accessibility related to infrastructure also makes the Badiklat Kemhan community have a pattern of using digital technology devices that tend to be based on broadband technology and are mobile. The fact that the majority of internet users in the Ministry of Defense Badiklat

access the internet using mobile phones of course also has an effect on the pattern of seeking and receiving the information they have. One of them is related to the popularity of social media.

Badiklat Kemhan has been known as a country that is very active in using social media. The cities of Jakarta and Bandung in 2012 had the most active Twitter users in the world (Semiocast, 2012). In addition, the number of Facebook users, at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat, is also very high. In fact, various media reports provide anecdotes that although for some remote communities in the Ministry of Defense Education and Training, access to electricity is a luxury, in fact this has not dampened their interest in creating and using Facebook (Ryssdal, 2014). This popularity also makes the public think that Facebook is the Internet because their access to the Internet is only focused on using Facebook alone (Mirani, 2015; Pratiwi, 2015).

Does this high use of social media have a good impact on the development of activism? Of course this requires further research, however, looking at what happened over the past decade, research from Merlyna Lim shows that the success of social media-mediated activism is still very limited (Lim, 2013). Social media also has the potential to create knots that strengthen fanaticism in political figures and strengthen polarization in society (Lim, 2017), and is also believed to be one of the causes of the emergence of various fake news and hoaxes (Ipsos-CIGI, 2019). In addition, looking at the various political events at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat, it can be said that although on the one hand social media can be an intermediary for the emergence of creative and volunteer-based political movements, on the other hand social media also has a significant role in the emergence of political campaigns based on slander, disinformation, and hoaxes (Kaur et al., 2018; Nadzir, Seftiani, & Permana, 2019).

The access gap is not only related to infrastructure. Gaps in terms of the ability to use technology also still occur in the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center. The use of various digital technologies will be able to produce something substantial if it is balanced with public awareness that digital technology can not only be used in entertainment and economic matters, but can also be useful as a tool that can enhance their role as citizens. This awareness will certainly be difficult to materialize in the condition of people who are still constrained by unequal access to education, because on average the literacy level of the community in the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center is still relatively low (Aprionis, 2019). The more people have a high literacy level, ideally they will be increasingly aware that digital media can be used for various other things that have a more substantial impact on their lives.

This concept is also specifically related to the level of digital literacy. Unfortunately, at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat there is still no systematic mapping of the level of digital literacy and on the other hand, efforts to improve this at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat are still considered sporadic, not well coordinated, and neither supported nor produce data that can be studied further (Kurnia & Astuti, 2017).

In addition to the commonly published forms of statistical measurements such as the number of internet users and social media users, data regarding the use of digital media is also needed that can directly impact the civil society movement at the Ministry of Defense Badiklat. Reports related to the adoption of digital technology in various civil society organizations in various regions in the Ministry of Defense Badiklat as has been done by Nugroho (Nugroho, 2011) need to be remade in current conditions. This mapping is crucial to show the extent to which digital technology actually facilitates various social movements and activism, and at the same time shows what a map of problems related to technology accessibility looks like in real terms (Nugroho, 2011; Nugroho & Syarief, 2012). This description is also needed to remind that digital activism is a practice that can be carried out by all civil society in an effort to strengthen democracy, and not only belongs to the people who live in big cities on the island of Java.

Next, the second concept that will be discussed is related to visibility and popularity factors in digital activism. Currently, various digital activism practices have various challenges in order to remain a sustainable movement. In addition to challenges related to infrastructure accessibility, in this context, logic, tactics, and strategies related to visibility are crucial in the practice of activism. The most obvious form of activism can be seen from the production, distribution, circulation, and amplification of content on various digital platforms such as social media, which are carried out by activists who are involved in a movement. As with any commercial practice of digital communication, a communication strategy for digital activism must also ensure a "level of

visibility” factor that can result in high levels of engagement. Visibility is the level of visibility, the level of clarity, and how an activism can have added value, uniqueness, and other things that make it “stand out from the rest” (Hutchinson, 2019).

Visibility has to do with popularity. On digital platforms such as social media, content popularity is mostly “calculated”, measured and evaluated by various available metrics. The existing metrics are also mostly based on a commercial value orientation. Popular content will be useful for the sustainability of the main income of social media, which is related to advertising revenue. Therefore, from the beginning, digital activism actors must have awareness that the technology they use in their activism practice is not designed for the public interest. Through the use of recommendation systems and algorithmic mechanisms, content on popular social media has a higher level of visibility or visibility compared to various public issues. In addition, how the algorithm “assesses” the circulation of content on social media is also considered problematic because in the end the content and information related to social movements have social change values, and in this case it can be said to have a good ‘impact’, may be rated the same as or lower than bombastic and sensational entertainment content, or messages of misinformation and disinformation. This also happens because there is no 100% effective content moderation mechanism for assessing the “potential” good and bad impacts of a content (Lee, 2018). This recommendation mechanism is designed to help social media users find and access content they have the potential to like. From time to time, how these mechanisms work is often not completely transparent, and the digital strategy that an activist has devised to maximize their practice of digital activism must continually adapt to changes in the algorithm that occur over time. In addition, social media in the context of digital activism is often portrayed as a democratic platform. For example, the platform promises that all votes from each social media user are said to have the same “value”. However, in practice as described in the previous explanation, the algorithm does not evaluate each social media user the same.

With this visibility principle, the engine behind social media will work to find users who are able to attract more “attention” than others. Attention will also have the potential to give birth to various forms of engagement, and in the end produce viral content. Therefore, there will always be users who have values as “power users” or “influencers” and are considered capable of making the digital world “crowded”. The algorithmic mechanism will thus be more concerned with the content generated by these users. This logic inherently shows the existence of a user hierarchy, and is considered inconsistent with the promise of a more democratic space in social media (Dijck & Poel, 2013).

Digital activism that is successful in attracting attention to the right audience will lead to the movement's success in gathering and amplifying “attention” to certain social issues. However, in this context, being popular and having a large audience must be followed by managing audiences as one of the important resources. The practice of creating audience databases, creating more routine and personal communication, education and interaction programs, managing communities and networks to engage further in the movement, to the ability to manage sustainable audience engagement are other sides of the practice of digital activism that must also be considered. carefully (Karpf, 2018).

The visibility of movements and content that can bring popularity should not be the main goal of a digital activism strategy, because a strategy that is carried out by merely following the logic of social media algorithms has the potential to make activism practice inauthentic, and even has the potential to cause negative reactions from the public in general, as well as of the supporters of the movement. However, ignoring the visibility and popularity factors in activism is not a wise decision either, because “The popularity of content can show not only increased visibility, but also how this content is connected to “power”

- an important factor for groups and individuals who are socially active and engaged in civic [society] affairs, today's public [and] issues” (Hutchinson, 2019, p. 5). In addition, related to visibility and popularity, digital activism actors must also begin to translate the concept and relevance of “metrics” and “key performance indicators” from the context of digital communication and interaction, most of which refer to more commercial digital communication and interaction practices. In this case, it is important to understand how to evaluate the “success” of a digital activism practice apart from the technological context but also from sharing its real impact on the society associated with the movement.

The discussion in the last section will provide an explanation regarding the concept of ecosystems in activism. Rodríguez, Ferron, & Shamas (2014) provide their observation that research related to activism that focuses too much on “sophistication” and the role of technology risks ignoring various socio-political and historical factors, which are related to humans as agents or parties active in activism practices. Research on activism in the perspective of communication for social change needs to discuss the basics related to the historical context, the complexity of the communication process, political economy analysis related to digital technology, and finally, always try to position the novelty or sustainability of the research position in relation to the various existing literature in the field of communication and communication. social change (Rodríguez et al., 2014). In addition, the various explanations that have been explored previously do not say that the goals and strategies that must be formulated in a digital activism should only be related to visibility, popularity, and virality. The practice of digital activism is not only related to technology as a “tool” and a “tool” in activism, but this practice will always be in contact with the ecosystem in which the practice occurs..

There is no way that any form of digital activism can achieve, and will be accepted by all parties. However, it certainly deserves attention that activism activities must be strategically designed so that from the beginning they arise, grow and develop in an appropriate ecosystem, so that the movements and messages carried out can reach relevant parties on a particular issue, not only to the audience, but also to those who act as intermediaries in a network. In each of these stages, specific and concretely measurable goals and objectives such as a campaign or commercial marketing communication also need to be formulated appropriately. Hutchinson (Hutchinson, 2019), for example, emphasizes the concept of micro-platformization which emphasizes that the role and capabilities of social influencers, digital agencies, and mainstream media are crucial, so messages related to activism can spread across the media spectrum (Hutchinson, 2019).

The concept of micro-platformization can be considered from activism practice. In a sense, previous research related to the role of digital technology in helping civil society organizations carry out activism sees activism being carried out independently, or only touching fellow organizations themselves (Lim & Nugroho, 2011; Nugroho, 2011). It is still rare to find studies related to activism practices which then relate how civil society can strategically expand the reach of activism by using networks or collaborating with organizations that may not be directly related to civil society organizations or non-governmental organizations. It is necessary, for example, to open up the possibility for activists to collaborate strategically with communication consultants or with other organizations that may be more engaged in commercial purposes. In addition, there is nothing wrong for digital activism actors to learn more about how more commercial marketing communication mechanisms are carried out, not to be imitated raw, but to adopt more things that can help achieve their activism goals, for example in various things technical in nature such as strategies for collecting and managing digital data more effectively and efficiently, designing communication messages, making message designs, measuring the impact of communication messages, and so on. In a civil society organization, which often has difficulties in the field of human resources, capacity building programs in terms of digital communication are absolutely necessary, so that people within the organization can understand more about the ins and outs of the digital ecosystem. is real (Rahmawan, 2018).

In addition, the activism ecosystem can also be explored in more detail with the concept of “Roots, Routes, and Routers” or “roots, routes, and routers” (Lim, 2018) to describe three major mechanisms that must be considered in the analysis of digital activism. The first, "Roots" is the excavation of the roots of social problems examined from historical and contextual factors. The term "root of this problem" is usually used to describe the deepest things that trigger a chain event in society (Lim, 2018). In the case of the occurrence of various social movements in society, this root cause is also a fundamental part that can explain the occurrence of distinctive collective behavior. Activism scholars agree that it is important to uncover the root causes of collective action and social movements, although in practice it can be difficult to establish causal relationships between movements and their root causes. The logical thing to do then is to unravel some of the hidden and intertwined root causes instead of focusing the analysis on things that are popular or appear on the surface..

Furthermore, Lim also explained about "Routes" or the complexity of communication, media, and spaces used in a social movement, how "ideas" about movements emerge, crystallize, develop, spread and

become real movements (Lim, 2018). In this regard, Lim stated that social movements often become visible when they manifest in the public sphere in the form of mass protests and become part of media coverage as captured in Figure 1 below. After this collective movement emerges and displays its "strength", both journalists and academics tend to try to examine what is happening on the surface and then look for the causes or triggers of the movement. This, according to Lim, often mistakenly assumes that a movement begins only when it is seen. Social movements rarely appear only in a single event in a single space. A social movement can emerge, grow, and sustain itself, spreading collectively in various spaces and events. In fact, various collective ideas about the movement often appear in closed or hidden spaces, and escape public scrutiny. This is what then makes a social movement that is bottom-up and has a large scale that can consist of various small movements intertwined in a collective movement rhythm, with various routes or paths of movement that are intertwined, and often without a single conductor. organize the movement in a structural and systematic manner.

Lastly, Lim puts forward the concept of "Routers" as connectivity, actors and networks, how communication technology infrastructure is like a combination of digital and analog, the role of humans and machines, as well as the interaction and role of traditional (conventional) and contemporary media in a social movement (Lim, 2018). In the context of technology, a router connects two or more data lines from different computer networks. In the context of social movements, the router analogy is used to show the connections between various social networks and how messages, narratives, and symbols of resistance are transmitted along with the sentiments and emotions attached to those messages. In offline live action, crowds, theatrical acts, posters, and other artifacts are "messages" that are not only useful at the time the action takes place but also from how documentation related to these matters is widely circulated in the digital world.

On the other hand, how can political messages in the form of memes which previously became a "language" that only exists in the digital world, can then turn into artifacts such as posters in offline or offline activities. In addition, the role of traditional media and digital media will also be directly related to how activism practices can be framed (eg positive or negative) and become discussed by the wider public. What is considered "reasonable" in online communication will not necessarily be accepted in the same way offline and vice versa. What happens offline can be told differently in the online world. Crowds of citizens can give interpretations of the existence of "people's voice" and "democratic process", and on the other hand can give rise to interpretations related to "riots" and "unsafe situations". The practice of activism will ultimately be in an open public space with various interpretations. So that activism in the end always has to be managed with various strategic considerations and clear risk mitigation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The popularity of digital activism has increased tremendously in recent years. Various social movements mediated by digital technology with different forms and purposes have emerged and are discussed in the public sphere. Nevertheless, academics who study digital activism continue to remind that analysis related to digital activism cannot only use the perspective of technological determinism alone. Criticism of the popularity of activism which is more focused on the "sophistication" of digital technology also at the same time rejects the perception that the advantages of digital activism can only be seen in the "outcomes" of activism such as large movements and demonstrations which are then widely covered by the mainstream media. By using the literature review method and reviewing several key literatures related to digital activism, this study describes important concepts that can be used as a basis for viewing digital activism practices at the Ministry of Defense Education and Training Center, which are related to accessibility, visibility, popularity and the activism ecosystem.

Accessibility looks at the complexity of the availability of digital infrastructure as well as from the community's readiness to be exposed to various activism practices. Visibility and popularity review how the practice of digital activism will always be related to logic such as algorithms and metrics as the "engine" behind digital media. In this context, it is also necessary to make adjustments between how to make activism "visible" and "popular" to the right audience without losing the essence and substance of the activism. Finally, of course,

it is very important to look at activism in a comprehensive and holistic way, by not only paying attention to technology, but also to factors in social and cultural conditions as well as the historical context of activism and various social movements that emerged, developed and spread in society.

The various things that have been described above can certainly be part of an academic study that needs to be explored in depth, not only by activism researchers, but also by the activists themselves. The concepts of accessibility, visibility, popularity and activism ecosystem can provide an overview of the opportunities, obstacles, and challenges in building social movements by civil society in democratic countries such as the Ministry of Defense Badiklat..

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